

Effect of Substituents on Extent of Hetero-Association in Solution. II. Trifluoroacetic Acid with Acetophenone

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The effect of substituted groups in acetophenone on the extent of its hetero-hydrogen bonding with trifluoroacetic acid in the non-volatile, non-polar solvent diphenylmethane was investigated at 30°. The substituents used were the bromo group, once on the methyl group of acetophenone in phenacyl bromide and once on the phenyl group in 4-bromoacetophenone, and the nitro group in 4-nitroacetophenone. The results show that the presence of any of these substituents will hinder the extent of complex formation between acetophenone and trifluoroacetic acid. The results also show that the hindrance is greatest in the case of $-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$ followed by $-\text{NO}_2$ and is, comparatively, the least in the case of $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}$.

A discussion is given for the relation between the varying powers of the substituents, to hinder the hetero-hydrogen bonding, and their inductive and resonance effects.

WE have reported¹ in part I of this series on the study of the effects of substituents on the extent of hetero-association of benzophenone with trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). Benzophenone itself was reported before² to cross-associate with TFA in solution in diphenylmethane to form non-volatile hetero-hydrogen bonded complexes. It was reported before^{2,3} also that TFA itself self-associates in the same solvent through hydrogen bonding. In our recent study¹ it was found that when the chloro or the bromo group is present as a substituted group in the benzophenone molecule, it decreases the extent of its hetero-association with TFA in solution. Since this type of study should prove useful and important, we extended the investigation to study the effect of substituents on the extent of hetero-hydrogen bonding of TFA with a different oxygen base, namely acetophenone. The difference in the nature of the phenyl and methyl groups adjacent to the carbonyl group made it easy to study the effect of the same bromo substituent when present on either of these groups. We also used the nitro group as another substituent of a different type to expand the comparison of the effect of the substituted groups.

No attempt was made at this stage, for lengthy calculations of equilibrium constants since the study was made on a semi-qualitative basis mainly to investigate the effect of the substituents.

Experimental

Materials :

Acetophenone and diphenylmethane were purified by vacuum distillation. Trifluoroacetic acid was purified by double distillation through a 30-plate

Oldershaw column at a reflux ratio in excess of 10 : 1, and only the middle portion was used. Phenacyl bromide, 4-bromoacetophenone and 4-nitroacetophenone were purified by double crystallization. After purification, all reagents were stored under vacuum.

Apparatus and Technique :

The method followed in this work was a vapour pressure method described previously⁴ in detail. It is based on the use of a certain evacuated vapour pressure apparatus constructed to measure the vapour pressure of the volatile constituents only of the solution present. Correlations are made between the measured vapour pressure and the extent of association of the species present in solution. In the present work we followed the same basic technique described in part I of this series¹.

Results and Discussion

The distribution of TFA into an equilibrium between liquid and vapour phases was discussed previously^{2,3} in the detailed calculations for the self-association of TFA. For the hetero-association of TFA with the phenones investigated in the present work, the same bases for treating experimental data and calculations discussed in detail in part I of this series¹, will also apply. f_A^t is the total formal concentration of TFA increment added in the presence of any of the phenones, Δf_A is that part of it tied up in non-volatile hetero-complexes and f_A^f is the remaining part of TFA free to self-associate, where :

$$\Delta f_A = f_A^t - f_A^f$$

Tables 1 to 4 include experimental values of total formal concentrations of added TFA, f_A^t , together

† Taken in part from M.Sc. thesis by Mrs. H. E. Abdel-Al, awarded in 1977.

with the calculated values of f_A^t and Δf_A . Each of Figs. 1 and 2 show comparative curves for the dependence of total pressure on formal concentrations of TFA in the presence of the same concentration of all the non-volatile solutes.

TABLE 1—DATA FOR ACETOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^t	Δf_A	f_A^t	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0085	0.0050	0.0070	0.0065
0.0270	0.0155	0.0115	0.0145	0.0125
0.0404	0.0235	0.0169	0.0220	0.0184
0.0539	0.0335	0.0204	0.0315	0.0224
0.0673	0.0455	0.0218	0.0377	0.0296
0.0808	0.0530	0.0278	0.0470	0.0338
0.0942	0.0675	0.0267	0.0565	0.0377
0.1077	0.0790	0.0287	0.0660	0.0417
0.1212	0.0900	0.0312	0.0770	0.0442
0.1346	0.1030	0.0316	0.0875	0.0471
0.1481	0.1150	0.0331	0.0980	0.0501
0.1615	0.1270	0.0345	0.1075	0.0540
0.1750	0.1390	0.0360	0.1200	0.0550
0.1885	0.1520	0.0365	0.1350	0.0535

TABLE 4—DATA FOR 4-NITROACETOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^t	Δf_A	f_A^t	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0090	0.0045	0.0080	0.0055
0.0270	0.0210	0.0080	0.0175	0.0095
0.0404	0.0320	0.0084	0.0240	0.0164
0.0539	0.0435	0.0104	0.0337	0.0202
0.0673	0.0550	0.0123	0.0415	0.0258
0.0808	0.0665	0.0143	0.0540	0.0268
0.0942	0.0790	0.0152	0.0645	0.0297
0.1077	0.0920	0.0157	0.0725	0.0352
0.1212	0.1040	0.0172	0.0845	0.0367
0.1246	0.1165	0.0181	0.0965	0.0381
0.1481	0.1290	0.0191	0.1080	0.0401
0.1615	0.1425	0.0190	0.1200	0.0415
0.1750	0.1560	0.0190	0.1325	0.0425
0.1885	0.1665	0.0220	0.1430	0.0455

The first conclusion drawn from the results is that acetophenone itself does cross-associate with TFA to form hetero-complexes, as is clear from the lowering in vapour pressures for the same f_A^t in the presence of acetophenone, as shown in curves (i) and (v) in both Figs. 1 and 2. This can be explained on the same basis as previous analogous results² obtained with benzophenone.

TABLE 2—DATA FOR PHENACYL BROMIDE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^t	Δf_A	f_A^t	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0120	0.0015	0.0110	0.0025
0.0270	0.0270	0.0020	0.0220	0.0050
0.0404	0.0360	0.0044	0.0320	0.0084
0.0539	0.0490	0.0049	0.0410	0.0129
0.0673	0.0610	0.0063	0.0515	0.0158
0.0808	0.0750	0.0058	0.0620	0.0188
0.0942	0.0875	0.0067	0.0725	0.0217
0.1077	0.1005	0.0072	0.0835	0.0242
0.1212	0.1140	0.0072	0.0940	0.0272
0.1346	0.1265	0.0081	0.1040	0.0306
0.1481	0.1385	0.0096	0.1140	0.0341
0.1615	0.1515	0.0100	0.1245	0.0370
0.1750	0.1650	0.0100	0.1370	0.0380
0.1885	—	—	0.1495	0.0390

TABLE 3—DATA FOR 4-BROMOACETOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^t	Δf_A	f_A^t	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0085	0.0050	0.0070	0.0065
0.0270	0.0160	0.0110	0.0155	0.0115
0.0404	0.0270	0.0134	0.0225	0.0179
0.0539	0.0375	0.0164	0.0320	0.0219
0.0673	0.0480	0.0193	0.0400	0.0273
0.0808	0.0610	0.0198	0.0480	0.0328
0.0942	0.0715	0.0227	0.0590	0.0352
0.1077	0.0835	0.0242	0.0685	0.0392
0.1212	0.0960	0.0252	0.0810	0.0408
0.1346	0.1090	0.0256	0.0920	0.0426
0.1481	0.1190	0.0291	0.1020	0.0461
0.1615	0.1330	0.0285	0.1150	0.0465
0.1750	0.1465	0.0285	0.1265	0.0485
0.1885	0.1575	0.0310	0.1385	0.0500

Fig. 1. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of TFA in presence of: (i) 0.0M non-volatile solute, (ii) 0.05M Phenacyl Bromide, (iii) 0.05M 4-nitroacetophenone, (iv) 0.05M 4-bromoacetophenone and (v) 0.05M Acetophenone.

Fig. 2. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of TFA in presence of: (i) 0.0M non-volatile solute, (ii) 0.1M Phenacyl Bromide, (iii) 0.1M 4-nitroacetophenone, (iv) 0.1M 4-bromoacetophenone, and (v) 0.1M Acetophenone.

The observed increase in values of f_A^i and corresponding decrease in values of Δf_A when using any of the substituted acetophenones (Tables 2 to 4), as compared to corresponding values using the same formal concentration f_A^i of TFA in the presence of unsubstituted acetophenone (Table 1) indicates that the presence of any of the investigated substituents in the acetophenone molecule hinders the extent of the hetero-hydrogen bonding of the latter with TFA. This means that each of these groups decreases the basic power of the carbonyl-oxygen, i.e., hinders the potency of the lone pairs of electron to bond this oxygen atom to the acidic proton of TFA, through hydrogen bonding.

The above conclusion can be explained on the basis of the induced effects resulting from the presence of the substituent groups in the acetophenone molecule. The bromo group is known to show a (-I) inductive effect and a (+R) resonance effect. In the case of phenacyl bromide, the (+R) effect will not be performing, since there are no π electrons adjacent to the bromine atom. The (-I) effect results in withdrawal of electron density towards the bromine atom, hence decreasing the density of the

lone pairs of electrons on the carbonyl-oxygen. This is opposed by the conjugative effect of the carbonyl group itself which results in an increase in the electron density on the carbonyl-oxygen. The fact that the bromo group in this position does decrease the ability of the carbonyl-oxygen to hydrogen bond to the acidic proton of TFA, as indicated from the results, means that the (-I) effect of the bromo group overcomes and surpasses the conjugative effect of the carbonyl group.

In the case of 4-bromoacetophenone, on the other hand, both the (-I) and (+R) effects of the bromo group will be functioning, together with the relatively weak (+I) effect of the methyl group. Both the latter effect and the (+R) effect of the

bromo group will result in increasing the electron density on the carbonyl-oxygen, thus opposing the (-I) effect of the bromo group. The fact that the bromo group in this position also does hinder the extent of hetero-hydrogen bonding indicates that the (-I) effect is more powerful in this case than the combined (+R) and (+I) effects.

The nitro group is known to show a (-I) and a (-R) effects, which will both be operating in the case of 4-nitroacetophenone, together with the (+I)

effect of the methyl group. In this case the nitro group will be withdrawing electron density towards itself through both of its effects, which will be opposed only by the relatively weak (+I) effect of the methyl group. It is expected then, and verified by the results, that the nitro group in this position will hinder the extent of hetero-association between acetophenone and TFA.

This type of study will also be very useful in comparing the relative effects of the substituent groups. It is clear from Figs. 1 and 2 that the extent of hetero-association is mostly decreased in

case of phenacyl bromide, followed by 4-nitroacetophenone than by 4-bromoacetophenone. This means that the sequence of the hindering effect is :

If we first compare the effect of the bromo group in both positions investigated, we find that its (-I) effect is weaker in 4-bromoacetophenone due, mainly, to the increase in distance between the carbonyl and the bromo groups. Also, the (+R) effect of the phenyl-bromo group is not paralleled by a similar effect in case of the methyl-bromo group. Both differences will lead then to a greater decrease in the basic power of the carbonyl-oxygen in the case of the methyl-bromo group than the phenyl-bromo group. Hence the former is expected to have a greater hindering effect on the extent of hetero-association, which is in accordance with the results (curves ii and iv).

Comparing the effects of the bromo group in phenacyl bromide and the nitro group in 4-nitroacetophenone, we find that the (-I) effect of the methyl-bromo group is being compared with a (-I) and a (-R) effects for the nitro group. All effects of both groups will result then, in decreasing the basic power of the carbonyl-oxygen. The (-I) effect of the nitro group is generally known, however, to be weaker than that of the bromo group. It becomes more weaker in this case because of the longer distance between the nitro and the carbonyl groups. This resulted in the fact that the combined

(-I) and (-R) effects of the nitro group were weaker than the (-I) effect of the bromo group in phenacyl bromide, which is clear from the results (curves ii and iii).

The remaining comparison is between the effects of the phenyl-bromo group and the nitro group. The distance is the same between either group and the carbonyl-oxygen. The phenyl-bromo group will show a (-I) effect *opposed* by a (+R) effect, whereas the nitro group will show a combined (-I) and (-R) effects operating in the same direction. Although the (-I) effect of the nitro group is weaker than that of the bromo group, the combined operating effects of either group will result in the nitro group hindering the extent of complex formation more than the phenyl-bromo group, as is clear from the results (curves iii and iv).

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